

MiniAERCam Avionics¹

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Abstract. This paper describes the architecture of a small, seven and a half (7.5) inch diameter, free-flyer satellite called the Mini-AERCam for Autonomous Extravehicular Robotic CAMera. NASA-JSC developed Mini-AERCam as a technology demonstrator for an astronaut assistant. This design allows inspections of the exteriors of the Space Shuttle or International Space Station, thereby reducing the number of Extra Vehicular Activities (EVA) and reducing crew workload.

The paper focuses on the architectural aspects of the design philosophy used to successfully achieve the seemingly mutually exclusive requirements specified for the Mini-AERCam. Key among the design approaches is the use of soft functions. Soft functions were used in the MiniAERCam to implement everything from peripherals to virtual Printed Circuit Board (PCB) traces. The paper discusses how soft functions can minimize the interactions between detail peripheral development and board level hardware development. Additionally, the use of soft function serves as a unifying focus point for the system architect, software designers and hardware designers. The soft function is where hardware and software designs can meld together to optimize overall system performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

MiniAERCam’s predecessor, “Sprint”, was flight tested on Space Shuttle flight STS-87 in 1997. As will be seen later, Sprint was a much larger and less aggressive design. By

contrast, the constraints imposed by the MiniAERCam system requirements dwarf the challenge of it’s predecessor. Sprint measures thirteen (13) inches in diameter and performs simplified, integer flight control laws. The technology available in 2000 would have allowed a smaller Sprint to be easily developed. It is an irony that as technology improves, system requirements increase just enough to offset the gain in technology, and so, the requirements growth for the second generation of the Astronaut assistant free-flyer far exceed those of Sprint. Not only was the size reduced to a seven and a half inch sphere, but Sprint’s simplified integer control laws were replaced with sophisticated, floating point control laws, digital Global Positioning System (GPS) filtering was added, Sprint’s two analog cameras were replaced with three digital cameras, video compression was added, and Sprint’s propulsion system was replaced with a harmonized propulsion system. Position hold was also added to the processor’s load. All the above technologies rely, to varying degrees, on the power of the new processor.

2. DESIGN DESCRIPTION

Figure 1 shows the exterior and cutaway views of the Mini-AERCam. The exterior view shows the GPS antenna at the top of the sphere. A little behind it, and out of sight on the exterior view but visible on the cut-away, is the antenna of the communication system. Farther down, below the GPS antenna, is an array of white LEDs which provide illumination.

Four thruster clusters girdle the satellite. Each of the clusters contains either 2 or 4 thrusters. Three of these clusters are shown in the exterior view. The thruster cluster shown in the center of the exterior view is designated as the forward cluster. The one on the left is the starboard thruster cluster. The one on the right is the port thruster cluster. The aft thruster cluster is hidden in the exterior view.

The forward thruster cluster holds two cameras, a VGA resolution and a high resolution camera, and two forward facing thrusters which provide longitudinal thrust. The starboard thruster cluster holds 4 tangentially mounted thrusters, that provide rotational thrust couples around the

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Figure 1 Exterior photograph and cutaway drawing of the MiniAERCam

vertical and lateral axis, and an on/off power switch which is suitable for use by a suited astronaut.

The port thruster cluster holds the 4 tangential mates to the starboard thruster cluster and a second VGA resolution camera. The aft thruster cluster holds 2 aft facing thrusters, a recharge port, and a refuel port.

The cut-away view shows the upper GPS antenna on the top of the sphere and the communications antenna just aft of it. The MEMS gyro resides below the top GPS, and the wireless Ethernet communication system resides below the MEMS.

The 3000 psi Xenon fuel tank and regulator is located in the center and is surrounded by the 7 Li-ion battery cells that provide the 4 hour mission time. The GPS system, shown below the fuel tank, is mounted as a daughter card on the Avionics Processor board. The Avionics Processor board provides the computation resources (see Table 2), secondary power generation and distribution, thruster drivers, and the hub for all data communications. The Video Compression board resides below the Avionics Processor. It controls the cameras, multiplexes and packetizes the video streams, provides hardware wavelet compression for the VGA resolution camera, and its DSP compresses the high resolution camera data. The lower GPS antenna resides at the bottom of the sphere.

3.0 DESIGN CONSTRAINTS

Although the requirements for the Mini-AERCam have grown, the physics of space flight and the volume of the seven and a half inch sphere dictate that the power, mass, and of course volume can not grow. In fact, it is preferable to reduce power and mass.

There are several additional major design constraints that drive the internal configuration and packaging of the Mini-AERCam vehicle. The physical constraints listed in Table 1 along with the thermal characteristics of the vehicle shell and associated internal plates [1] drive the placement and configuration of the avionics.

TABLE 1. Physical Constraints

Constraints	Sprint	Mini-AERCam
Power (Watts)	27	18.2
Weight (Kg)	16.1	4.7
Diameter (Inches)	13	7.5
Volume (liters)	18.8	3.62

It should be noted that the ability of the vehicle to dissipate waste heat is constrained by the requirement to eliminate any sharp protrusions, which might cause damage in the event of a collision with another vehicle or structure. This requirement effectively eliminates the use of thermal

radiators for dissipating waste heat. This leaves thermal radiation and the thermal mass of the vehicle as the only ways to manage the waste heat. These methods are effective for a limited time. Consequently, the battery capacity, fuel load, and thermal mass are all designed to meet a four (4) hour mission. Within the four hours sufficient fuel and battery capacity exists and the vehicle will remain within its thermal limits. Operation beyond the four hour limit carries the obvious risk.

performance constraints are combined with the physical constraints very little design leeway remains.

5.0 DESIGN STRATEGY

It was clear from the outset that satisfying the MiniAERCam Avionics performance and functionality requirements while staying within the constraint limits would not only be a challenge, but would carry significant risk for failure. As a consequence, a defensive design strategy was developed for MiniAERCam that incorporated maximum flexibility and fall backs. Key technology elements of the strategy are the use of reconfigurable devices and distributed architecture. More philosophical elements of the strategy involve the incorporation of synergistic options into the design to mitigate the impact of design mistakes on the design, schedule, and budget. For example, the MPC740 was not chosen because it was an embedded version of the PowerPC. In fact the embedded label was a very minor factor in the choice. Two major issues were at the root of the MPC740 selection. At the time, radiation hardened PowerPC's, the 603e and the 750, were in development, but they would not be available for at

4.0 PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS

The avionics performance requirements for the MiniAERCam are listed in Table 2. The design of MiniAERCam started only 3 ½ years after Sprint flew, nevertheless, MiniAERCam's performance requirements are orders of magnitude more demanding than Sprint's requirements. Even in terms of higher performance systems, such as the International Space Station's 2.3 MIPS and 16 MB computers (Multiplexer/DeMultiplexer (MDM)), the MiniAERCam far exceeds these systems too. These requirements, in and of themselves, do not constitute a serious constraint on the design choices, but when the

TABLE 2. Capability Comparisons

Capability		Sprint	Mini-AERCam
Processor			
MIPS	1	488 @ 266 MHz	
SPECfp95 (est)	-	6.9 @ 266 MHz	
Memory			
RAM	32 KBytes	64 Mbytes w/EDAC	
Cache	-	32 KB data 32 KB instruction	
Non-volatile	64 KBytes	8 MBytes	
Serial Bus			
RS-232	3 @ 9600 baud	1 @ 19200 baud	
I ² C	-	2 @ 1Kbps	
RS-422	-	2 @ 10 Mbps	
LVDS	-	16 @ 10 Mbps	
Instrumentation			
ADCs	16 ADCs w/6 SCAs	16 ADCs (MEMS)	
Distributed	-	2 I ² C	
Video			
Cameras	2 analog	digital	1 High Resolution 1280x960 2 VGA Resolution 640x480
Compression	-	2 Wavelet ICs 1 DSP	
Data pipe	RS-170 analog	UDP packets	
Illumination	Incandescent	White LED Array	
Batteries			
Main	15.3 Ah Li ion @ 20v	5.5 Ah Li ion @ 29.2 volts	
Illumination	5.1 Ah Li ion	(rechargeable)	
Propulsion			
Propellant	Nitrogen @ 3000 psi	Xenon @ 3000 psi (refuel capability)	
Thrusters	12	12 (harmonized)	
Communications			
GPS	-	Differential	
Radiation Tolerance	Commercial parts	Commercial Part with a path to Rad Tolerant/Hard parts	

least 2 years. There was no guarantee that either part would be successful. In addition, the commercial availability of the integrated circuit was questionable. At the same time we were debating both the need for the additional performance of a 750 and the need to reduce board space and Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) pinouts by reducing the memory to 32 bits. At the time MPC740 was not being discussed as a design candidate, but it turned out to be the solution. What the MPC740 offers is a 750 architecture in a 603e footprint. So no matter which radiation hardened part ultimately became available, and regardless of whether a 32 or a 64 bit memory architecture was chosen, the prototype boards built for the 740 could be used to continue development.

two years. In the interim a commercial 1 million gate (400k gate typical) SRAM based FPGA was chosen for the prototype. The FPGA implements most of the soft functions and virtually all the virtual PCB traces. To a lesser extent, the Reset Controller, which is also a FPGA, albeit a much smaller one, fulfills the same function in a non-volatile part capable of boot strapping the Avionics Processor Board start up.

5.1 RECONFIGURABLE DEVICES

As can be seen in figure 2, nearly all of the Avionics Processor components are reconfigurable to one degree or another. Central to the Avionics Processor architecture is the Processor FPGA. Just as in the case of the processor, a large, commercially available, radiation hardened, or at least radiation tolerant, FPGA would not be available for at least

5.2 SOFT FUNCTIONS

The use of standard, non-configurable integrated circuits (IC's) would mean that several standard IC's would be needed to provide the functionality that can be embedded into a single configurable device such as a FPGA. Additionally, power and space is usually wasted because it is highly unlikely that each of the standard IC's contains exactly the functionality that is needed; in exactly the form that is needed. As a result, some functionality and pins on the standard IC's go unused. Worse still, additional IC's may have to be added to condition the Input/Output (I/O) of the standard IC's.

Figure 2 Avionics Processor Board Architecture emphasizes soft functions and virtual PCB routing

On the other hand, non-configurable devices do not require additional Intellectual Property (IP), which lowers the initial cost of standard IC's, whereas the initial cost of reconfigurable devices can be very high due to the expensive IP embedded into the FPGA. This is of particular concern for aerospace systems where the cost is amortized over a small production run. Nevertheless, the use of reconfigurable devices offer several offsetting benefits which can reduce schedule, cost, and risk. In the case of MiniAERCam, the processor FPGA was used to minimize the space and power consumed by implementing the minimum set of peripherals as soft functions customized to the precise needs of the Avionics Processor Board (APB). Since the soft functions are a tailored, minimum set of functions, all the VHDL code was written in house. Table 3 lists the VHDL coded soft functions that reside in the processor FPGA along with the associated logic cell size. A total of 11999 of the 16640 logic cell are used.

The cost of producing this tailored set of peripherals can be further reduced by implementing only the required features. For example, the MiniAERCam Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter (UART) does not implement any of the modem control functionality found in the full feature UARTs available in standard IC's. Further, any anomaly to the function can also be resolved by reprogramming the FPGA.

Table 3: SoftFunctions

Function	Logic Cells
Comm System Interface	178
Interrupt Controller	381
I ² C Controller	1770
LVDS Controller (defaults for spare)	9
Memory	1028
MEMS Gyro Controller	1118
Thruster Drivers	4687
Timers	698
UARTs	1288
Utility	192
Video Controller	602

Of course there are sometimes unique functions that can not be implemented easily with standard IC's. In these cases the FPGA proves to be indispensable. As an example, MiniAERCam's thruster controller [1] is unique. The controller must be able to precisely position a thruster firing, precisely time its duration, and provide a watchdog to make sure the thruster does not fire too long. It must do this because the Avionics processor is asleep 90% of the time in order to conserve power. This is not a capability normally found in COTS ICs.

5.3 VIRTUAL PCB TRACES

Serious consideration is not only given to mitigating the risks associated with peripheral functionality, but also with mitigating the risks linked to PCB routing errors.

In many designs, bit and byte alignment have caused serious confusion and rework. Prime culprits are byte swapping between Intel and Motorola formats, and big endian versus little endian bit ordering. This type of mistake can cause massive bus layout problems necessitating the cost and delay associated with the layout and manufacture of a new board. For these and other potential design issues a FPGA is used to move as much board connectivity as possible from the board to the FPGA. In effect, the FPGA serves as virtual PCB traces. This allows most routing errors to be resolved by reprogramming the FPGA rather than producing a new version of the board.

6.0 CONCURRENT DEVELOPMENT

The Avionics Processor Board was designed from the first to implement all of the processor's peripherals and interfaces in the Processor FPGA. This includes the PowerPC interface to the rest of the FPGA and beyond to the Avionics Processor board.

All the early planning and development carried the hardware and the FPGA IP forward together. The early definition of the PowerPC interface and the processor peripheral soft functions allowed the hardware development to be split into two parts, board design and IP development, with minimum risk. At the point where the two designs split, the preliminary hardware design and interface definitions were given to the board design team while the IP architecture, specification, and early pseudo code was given to the IP development team. The design of the board was, for the most part, divorced from the development of the VHDL code for the soft functions after the definition phase was complete. The successful execution of these tasks as separate parallel tasks depends on the quality of the initial definition of the soft functions and interfaces and the ability of the soft function to be modified to buffer the impact of any mistakes in the initial soft function definition or the implementation of the hardware design. The success also depends on constant communications between the hardware designer and the IP developer during hardware/software integration. However, the IP developer's job does not end there. As shown in figure 3 the IP forms the reconfigurable glue between the fixed hardware design and the Board Support Package (BSP) that contains the drivers used by the operating system to interface the applications to the hardware. IP plays a crucial role in optimizing and expediting the development of the interface to the BSP. So in the end, the modifications to the hardware are mitigated by two layers of programmability, the IP and the BSP.

Figure 3 Virtual MiniAERCam Processor

7.0 SUMMARY

It took 21 months, from project go ahead, to develop MiniAERCam's requirements, architecture, and a running 22 layer Avionics Processor Board. The processor, memory, power supplies, and serial buses on MiniAERCam's 22 layer Avionics Processor Board were operational after the addition of four (4) jumper wires. These four design errors were beyond the reach of function or routing reprogramming. Over the next six months of testing, hardware/software integration, and integration with other systems, design tweaks were made to the VHDL. The rest of the issues with the processor, memory, power sequencing, and serial buses were taken care of by either reprogramming the function or rerouting the signal. The funds reserved for additional board design iterations were returned to the project.

In one final turn of events, the communications system being designed for MiniAERCam failed to meet schedule and budget. Further, it was determined that the communication system would jeopardize the whole project. In a four (4) month period, while the rest of the system integration was performed, the MiniAERCam avionics was

redesigned to accept a wireless Ethernet system. In the process, a virtual ISA (Industry Standard Architecture) little endian space was implemented in the Processor FPGA of the big endian Avionics processor. The output from the virtual ISA space was serialized and sent via a Low Voltage Differential Signaling (LVDS) channel to a newly designed LVDS to PCMCIA bridge.

All of this change in functionality was accomplished without changing a trace on any of the existing printed circuit boards or changing a single wire in any of MiniAERCam's extensive cable harnesses. This is strong testimony to the ability of this architecture to accommodate even wildly unforeseen impacts.

REFERENCES

- [1] Larry Abbott, David Jochim, and Robert Shuler, "Avionics for a Small Satellite," *SPACE TECHNOLOGY AND APPLICATIONS INTERNATIONAL FORUM (STAIF-2001)*, February 11 - 15, 2001.

Dr. Larry Abbott has been with NASA for 31 years, first with NASA's Dryden Flight Research Center and then with NASA's Johnson Space Center. In between, he taught microprocessor based system design for 2.5 years at the Naval Postgraduate School. While at JSC he worked for 10 years on the development of the computer and data communication systems on the International Space Station, first as the System Development Manager in Engineering and then in the Command and Data Handling hardware lead in the Program Office. Following this assignment, he worked on the Avionics Upgrade for the Space Shuttle. During this assignment he developed the concept for the Universal Mini-Controller which he continued to develop. MiniAERCam is his latest assignment. He has a BSEE from U.C. Berkeley, a MS in System Management from the University of Southern California, a MS in Engineering from the California State University at Northridge, and a Doctor of Engineering from the University of Kansas.

